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Hybrid Opto-Thermocycler for RT-qPCR detects SARS-CoV-2

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. JLGC is an employee of F. Hoffmann-La Roche.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. Detailed information about 3D designs of all the parts, as well as the Arduino and Android applications can be found in GitHub [https://github.com/BioARTS-Lab/Hybrid-Opto-Thermocycler-for-RT-qPCR-detects-SARS-CoV-2-](https://github.com/BioARTS-Lab/Hybrid-Opto-Thermocycler-for-RT-qPCR-detects-SARS-CoV-2)

Ethics approval statement

This study was reviewed and approved by the Committee on Bioethics for Research in Human Beings (COBISH) of Cinvestav (No. 062/2020).

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Abstract

Although RT-qPCR is the gold standard for detecting the virus SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the scarcity of instruments, devices, and reagents for PCR testing in constrained settings. At least for under-resourced countries, it has become critical to deploy instruments that can be rapidly constructed and satisfy this demand. Instead of separating the optical system from the thermal module (typical of qPCR thermocyclers), here, we report a portable thermocycler —dubbed HybOT Cycler— that takes advantage of the high-temperature tolerances (>100 °C) of electronic and optical components to combine thermal control, illumination, and fluorescence detection into a highly integrated hybrid module. This simple configuration allowed us to reduce the overall number of components, thus simplifying its assembly and reducing the instrument size. The HybOT Cycler is wirelessly controlled from an application installed in a tablet. PCR assays are carried out in a bubble-free microfluidic device that can be easily replicated from an acrylic mold. Using our HybOT Cycler, we were able to detect down to 100 copies/ μL of genetic material of the virus SARS-CoV-2 with 95% sensitivity and 100% specificity. Our HybOT Cycler can assist in diagnosing SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens in resource-poor settings.

1. Introduction

Real-Time Quantitative Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-qPCR) remains the gold standard for detecting the virus SARS-CoV-2^[1,2] and other infectious diseases^[3]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, early diagnosis —achieved mainly by RT-qPCR— demonstrated to be crucial for proper disease and infection management^[4]. In highly industrialized countries where testing is not restricted to central laboratories (e.g., Germany^[5], Australia^[6] and the UK^[7]), the number of cases and deaths was remarkably reduced due to early detection strategies^[8]. In contrast, in developing countries, samples are transported to a handful of centralized laboratories for PCR diagnosis. For example, at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, Nepal^[9] and the Republic of Zimbabwe^[10] had only a single testing facility for the whole country. The lack of laboratories reduces the number of tests, leading to inadequate control of the virus propagation, causing delays in identifying and isolating infected people or providing them with medical^[11].

COVID-19 has exhibited marked global health inequalities and evidenced vulnerabilities in the supply chain of diagnostic devices^[12]. Since major lockdowns were imposed to prevent the spread of the disease, health supply chains have been disrupted, thus hampering shipping and procurement of diagnostic tests and instruments, leading to their scarcity^[12]. For qPCR, large-scale testing represents a global challenge because instruments are expensive, require frequent maintenance, and technical support is not readily available in every city^[13]. Therefore, rapidly deploying cost-effective and scalable technologies could be a practical solution to carry out a large number of diagnostic tests necessary for proper disease management, especially in countries with under-resourced healthcare systems^[10,14–16].

Frugal innovation in healthcare aim to make medical technologies accessible in low- or middle-income countries or situations with constrained resources, such as rural areas. Frugal instruments and devices are characterized by low cost and reduced complexity, compared to their commercial counterparts, trying to maintain optimal test functionality and quality, in addition to offering sustainability and scalability^[17]. Progress in frugal innovation has been boosted by the proliferation and low cost of digital fabrication tools, such as 3D printing, micromilling, and laser cutting. These tools have been used to manufacture point-of-care (POC) instruments for nucleic acid amplification (including PCR)^[18–22] or produce microfluidic molds or devices from a variety of materials —glass^[23] and plastics^[24,25] included—. Digital manufacturing technologies enable distributed manufacturing, where goods are produced locally, attuned to the requirements of the local market^[26]. This characteristic allows them to bypass the vulnerabilities in the supply chains of medical devices^[27], which has never been more evident than in the current pandemic^[28]. Altogether, the relative accessibility and low cost of digital manufacturing tools —empowered by the maker movement^[27]— enable health-care democratization.

Attempts at producing frugal instruments for qPCR with integrated fluorescence detection have been made. However, some instruments lack simplicity in design and construction because they integrate expensive optical components such as lasers, photodiodes, photomultipliers, lenses, and precision machined parts^[29–31] or complicated electronic control boards^[20,29–32]. Although significant progress has been made in developing low-cost and simple fluorescence detection systems, for example, using light-emitting diodes (LEDs) and smartphone cameras equipped with optical filters^[18,19,21,22,33–35], most of these platforms do not possess the thermal cycling capabilities required for RT-qPCR. Indeed, integrated thermal cyclers with fluorescence detection, still use complicated optical setups or require expensive semiconductor techniques to fabricate the PCR

chambers^[20,29]. These features complicate their manufacturing, replication, and adoption, preventing their widespread implementation in resource-constrained settings.

Microfluidic devices for PCR offer several advantages over conventional PCR tubes, such as small size, fast thermal cycling, reduced sample and reagent volumes, low cost, integration with sample preparation, among others^[36]. However, for several years a significant limitation of these devices has been the readily formation of air bubbles due to: incorrect pipetting, evaporation^[37], or uneven surface wetting^[38], which reduce PCR efficiency and throughput. Several strategies have recently been developed to mitigate or eliminate the appearance of bubbles in microfluidics^[37–40], making their operation more reliable.

Here, we describe a portable instrument for RT-qPCR that integrates a thermocycler and a fluorescent detection system into a compact hybrid module. The instrument runs bubble-free microfluidic devices to perform PCR assays. The instrument and the microfluidic device mold are produced mainly with two digital fabrication tools: a 3D printer and a CNC milling machine, each of which can be purchased for as little as US\$250. To demonstrate the robustness of our platform, we analyzed samples of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 and compared the performance with a commercial thermocycler, achieving 95% sensitivity and 100% specificity.

2. Materials and Methods

Instrument. All the components resided in a 3D-printed housing (24 x 14 x 10 cm). The heating system consisted of a stack of a Thermo Electric Cooler (TEC1-12715, Wakefield-Vette), a heat sink (1335, Adafruit), and a tangential fan (THA0412AD, Delta electronics). The optical excitation configuration comprised an array of four high-power LEDs (LXML-PB02, Phillips Lumileds) with a peak intensity at 470-nm and a 483-nm optical filter (67-028, Edmund Optics). An LED driver (COM-13705, Sparkfun) controlled the LEDs and was powered by a DC-DC converter (XL6019, Unit Electronics). A 3D-printed head housed an infrared sensor (MLX90615, Melexis), an array of 4 digital photodetectors (VEML6030, Vishay), and a 435-nm optical glass filter (67-031, Edmund optics). The 3D-printed parts included self-aligning structures that facilitated the assembly of all the pieces. A microcontroller (ABX00034, Arduino) incorporating a Bluetooth RF transceiver (HC-06, Wavesen) controlled the electronics and the sensors. A Graphical User Interface (GUI) was programmed (MIT App Inventor) to capture the PCR parameters and display the results. The GUI

was installed in a Tablet (Galaxy Tab A, Samsung). A 12-VDC 12.5-A power supply (ALM150PS12, XP Power) energized the whole system, while an H-bridge driver circuit (DC 43A Double BTS7960B, Diymore) drove the TEC. Finally, the microfluidic device was connected to a vacuum pump (MR370BPM, MIROU).

Microfluidic device. An acrylic mold (1.3mm thickness, ME303018, GoodFellow) was fabricated using a CNC milling machine (MDX-40A, Roland) with a 0.5 mm drill bit (1600.0197.118, Kyocera) at a one mm/s feed rate and 15000 rpm spindle speed. The mold was placed in a petri dish with 3 mL of chloroform for 5 min in order to eliminate any roughness on the structures caused by the milling process^[41]. Devices were fabricated by pouring polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS, Sylgard 184, Corning) on the mold at a 10:1 base to curing agent ratio (w/w). The devices were cured for 40 min at 80 °C in a convection oven. Replicas were cut out, peeled off, and the inlets and outlets were punched using a punching machine (Accu-Punch MP, Syneo). The PDMS chip and the coverslip (2850-18, Corning) were plasma-activated (Zepto, Diener) for 1 min and then sealed. A thermocouple (CHAL-003-BW, Omega, USA) and a thermocouple-to-digital converter (MAX6675, Maxim Integrated, USA) were used to monitor the temperature in the chambers.

Degassing experiments. We modified the instrument head and replaced the lid with a transparent material to allow image acquisition of the microchambers during the experiments, **Figure S1**. 100 μ L of master mix (TaqMan, Universal PCR Master Mix, 4304437, Roche) and 2 μ L of blue food dye (Food dye, McCormick, USA) were mixed with 100 μ L of sterile Milli-Q water and centrifuged for 10 s at 6000 rpm. 6.5 μ L of the mixture was injected into the four reaction chambers and sealed with optical adhesive film. Four different times (0, 3, 6, and 9 min) were tested at five pressure conditions (250, 350, 450, 650, and 950 mbar) using a vacuum transducer (901P-11034, Micro Pirani-Piezo Loadlock Vacuum Transducer) and three different vacuum pumps (ROB-10398, Sparkfun; 400-3910 Barnant Company; and H004C-11, Parker). The degassing conditions were performed at 30°C, followed by the initial denaturation step for 10 min at 95°C. Photographs were acquired throughout the experiment. All experimental conditions were repeated three times.

Fluorescence experiments. Solutions of Fluorescein (2321-07-5, Sigma-Aldrich) were prepared in PBS (14040-133, Thermo Fisher) at 1, 0.8, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, and 0.2 μ M and injected into the microfluidic chambers. Fluorescence micrographs were obtained with an inverted microscope

using a 10x objective (Axio Observer A1, Carl Zeiss) with an exposure time of 100 ms. Meanwhile in the HybOT, the exposure time was set to 200 ms per cycle.

SARS-CoV-2 detection. 30 samples in total were obtained via nasopharyngeal swabs, 20 came from individuals who tested positive for the virus and 10 samples from healthy individuals used as a control cohort. Total viral RNA was extracted from these samples using the Viral RNA Purification Kit (RNAv-090, BIOPURE, Mexico). We used the CDC protocol for RT-qPCR to confirm the presence of SARS-CoV-2. To fill four reaction chambers, the solutions are introduced by pipetting and 40 μ L RT-qPCR reactions were set as follows: 20 μ L of master mix (KAPA SYBR FAST qPCR 2X, KK4650, KAPA Biosystems,) were added to 12.8 μ L of molecular grade sterile distilled water (7732-18-5, Fisher BioReagents), 0.8 μ L of RT Mix (50X KAPA RT Mix, KK4650, KAPA Biosystems), 0.8 μ L of ROX (ROX, KK4650, KAPA Biosystems), 0.8 μ L of Reverse primer (10 μ M), 0.8 μ L of Forward primer (10 μ M) and 4 RNA samples of 1 μ L. The sequences of primers were as follows: N1-F (5'-GAC-CCC-AAA-ATC-AGC-GAA-AT-3') and N1-R (5'-TCT-GGT-TAC-TGC-CAG-TTG-AAT-CTG-3').

For calibration curves, serial dilutions of *in vitro* transcribed SARS-CoV-2 N1 RNA^[42] quantified beforehand were used employing the same protocol and RT-qPCR reagents used for real samples (protocol in Supplementary Information). The inlet and outlet ports of the device were sealed with an optical adhesive film (4311971, Applied Biosystems). A drop of mineral oil (M5904, Sigma) was placed between the device and the thermocycler plate. The thermal cycling program includes a combined degasification and reverse transcription steps for 5 min at 42°C, an initial denaturation step for 3 min at 95°C, and 40 amplification cycles (denaturation: 95°C, 18 s; annealing/extension 60°C, 45 s) for a total assay time of 50 min. This study was reviewed and approved by The Committee on Bioethics for Research in Human Beings (COBISH) of Cinvestav (No. 062/2020).

Data Analysis. Fluorescence data were recovered from the tablet, and analyzed and plotted in either MATLAB (2020b, MathWorks) or Prism6 (GraphPad Software, USA). For threshold calculation, first, the baseline values were obtained from the fluorescence intensities of all the wells from all experiments for the first cycles (3-10), when not enough amplicons have been produced. Next, the thresholds were defined as the baseline plus 10 standard deviations. The C_T values were obtained when the fluorescence intensity of each amplification curve crossed the defined threshold. Calibration curves were generated by plotting the C_T against the number of copies per μ L.

PCR efficiencies of both systems were calculated by varying the threshold, ranging 0.1-0.5 of normalized fluorescence intensities. Next, calibration curves at each threshold were generated. The slope of each calibration curve was used to calculate the efficiency (e) according to $e=10^{-(1/\text{slope})}$. The theoretical efficiencies were plotted against the normalized threshold.

Sensitivity and specificity analysis were performed by comparing the results provided by the benchtop system (actual class) against the results obtained from the HybOT system (predicted class) through a confusion matrix. True positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) were quantified, and the sensitivity and specificity values were calculated according to the following formulas: $\text{sensitivity}=\text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FN})$ and $\text{specificity}=\text{TN}/(\text{TN}+\text{FP})$.

3. Results and Discussion

Design of the Hybrid Opto-Thermocycler. Our portable qPCR instrument seamlessly integrates temperature control and illumination into a single hybrid module that simultaneously transfers heat and shines light to microfluidic chambers, **Figure 1a**. Each microchamber is sandwiched between a light source and a detector, thus: (i) simplifying the design of the Opto-mechatronic system, (ii) facilitating the alignment of all the components, and (iii) eliminating the need for external optical parts, such as lenses, optical fibers or pinholes. The hybrid module consists of an aluminum plate housing four high-power LEDs covered by an excitation glass filter (483 nm). This machined aluminum plate sits on top of a Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) that heats or cools the aluminum plate. The excitation filter serves two purposes: it conducts heat generated by TEC to the microfluidic chip and filters the light from the LEDs. Notably, although both the optical and electronic components are subjected to high temperatures ($\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$), they do not exceed their maximum operating parameters. A separate 3D-printed lid houses the fluorescence detection system and consists of four digital light detectors and a small fan. These detectors are mounted on a PCB that sits on an emission glass filter (535 nm). Below this filter is an infrared (IR) sensor, located at the center of the light detectors, that measures the temperature of the heating plate

(i.e., the excitation filter), **Figure 1b,c**. When closed, the lid pushes over the microfluidic device, securing it in place and blocking outside light into the system, **Figure 1d**. In summary, light travels from the LEDs, passes through the optical filter, the microfluidic chambers, the emission filter (in that order), and reaches the light sensors.

Figure 1. Engineering of the Hybrid Opto-Thermocycler (HybOT). (a) Cartoon shows the concept behind HybOT. Heat is produced with a Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) while light is generated with a high-power LED array that illuminates the microfluidic device through an excitation filter. The LEDs tolerate the high temperatures produced by the TEC. Note that heat and light are generated from the bottom and travel upwards. Emitted light from the fluorescent amplicons is detected by a light sensor through an emission filter. (b) Exploded view off all the components showing their location. For easier comprehension, the system is divided into a Lid and the HybOT. The lid contains the light sensors, the emission filter, and the Infrared (IR) sensor; while the HybOT contains the TEC, LEDs, and the excitation filter. (c) Cross-section view of all the parts in the assembled instrument. (d) Photograph of the instrument. Insets shows the lid closed and the microfluidic device. (e) Block diagram of the components inside the instrument. Arrows show the communication direction between the sensors, LEDs, vacuum pump (VP), actuators, electronics, and the microcontroller.

Notably, the instrument is assembled from standard optical and electronic components (**Table S1**) which contrary to specialized. All the mechanical parts, the casing, and the microfluidic mold are produced with a 3D-printer and a CNC milling machine. One advantage of digital fabrication tools is their relatively low price compared to commercial real-time thermocyclers. For example, the price for an entry 3D printer and CNC milling machine can be as low as \$180 USD (Voxelab Aquila) and \$240 (Comgrow Robo 3018) for each tool, respectively, which together is significantly lower than the cost of commercial real-time thermocyclers. Furthermore, these machines can be found in most universities, high schools, or city workshops known as fab labs. The number of fab labs has grown exponentially during the last decade and can now be found in resource constrained settings including rural areas and developing countries^[43]. Fab labs have played a vital role during the COVID-19 pandemic by being able to locally manufacture medical equipment in diverse countries such as Italy^[43] and Tunisia^[44]. Moreover, the hardware and the off-the shelf components that we employed to assemble our HybOT Cycler, do not necessarily become scarce during a catastrophe, as opposed to specialized scientific or medical equipment, and these components are most of the time in stock at local shops. Finally, the bonding of the PDMS chip to glass via surface activation with oxygen plasma can be replaced by more inexpensive methods, such as surface activation with corona discharge or UV/Ozone treatment, or through adhesive-based bonding^[45]. Therefore, we expect that the HybOT Cycler can be assembled in a broad range of settings, even resource-constrained ones.

We developed an Android application specifically to control the HybOT remotely. The application is downloaded into a tablet or smartphone and communicates with our instrument via Bluetooth, relaying temperature cycle parameters and retrieving fluorescence data. The application features a user-friendly graphical interface to display the fluorescence values of each chamber, the temperature of the device, and fields to enter the PCR cycle parameters, **Figure S2**. The total weight of the instrument is 1 Kg. The system's operation starts by turning a single power switch and placing a bubble-free microfluidic device loaded with the PCR solution.

The instrument contains a microcontroller (Arduino) that runs a digital proportional–integral–derivative (PID) temperature controller to regulate the TEC actuation, **Figure 1e**. It also synchronizes the activation of the power LEDs and the readings of the light sensors. A miniature vacuum pump, placed inside the instrument, is connected to the microfluidic device to apply negative pressure during the PCR assay, **Figure S3**. A key advantage of our instrument is that it

can be disassembled and reassembled relatively quickly, and thus maintenance would be straightforward. Furthermore, the HybOT consists of only 15 parts that are easy-to-assemble; an exploded view of these parts is shown in **Figure 1b, S4-S7**.

Bubble-free microfluidic device. The appearance of air bubbles during a PCR assay in a microfluidic device can reduce its efficiency^[46], modify the final injected volume and alter reagent concentrations^[47]. Also, bubble expansion can expel the reagents away from the chambers or lead to a thermal gradient within them^[38]. Finally, bubbles can interfere with the optical readout due to light reflection or refraction^[48]. Several strategies have been proposed to mitigate the formation of bubbles but are either too impractical^[49,50] or not efficient^[38].

Air bubbles can be accidentally introduced when loading the sample into the chip or form during the thermal cycles heating process. Being gas permeable^[51], PDMS has proven to be an effective material to remove bubbles in microfluidic channels. Thus, to achieve bubble-free PCR assays, we engineered a device —inspired by previous reports^[37,52]— that consisted of PDMS microfluidic chambers surrounded by a vacuum channel (**Figure 2a, b**). By sustaining a negative pressure around our microfluidic chambers, the gas bubbles in the chambers diffuse through the PDMS wall (1mm thick) until they reach the vacuum channel and thus are purged^[37,52]. Our device contains four PCR reaction chambers with a diameter of 3 mm and a height of 1 mm for a total volume of 6.5 μL , **Figure 2a**. Each chamber has an inlet and an outlet, and is surrounded by a horseshoe vacuum channel (height and width of 1 mm) that degasses the PCR chambers during the thermal cycles preventing bubble formation. The chamber's vacuum channels are joined to a shared inlet, that is in turn connected to a vacuum pump located inside the instrument, **Figure 2b**. For the degassing step, the user only inserts the microfluidic device to the vacuum pin in the chip holder, **Video S1**.

Instead of using photolithography to fabricate master molds, we made an acrylic mold with a milling machine using a single drill bit, **Figure S8**. (Entry-level milling machines are readily available in most countries at an affordable price^[24]). PDMS replicas can be made from this mold at once. The replicas are then bonded to a glass coverslip that fits into the heating plate, **Figure 2c**. Our PDMS/glass device possesses better thermal conductivity (coverslip 1.4 and PDMS 0.27 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) than polypropylene (0.22 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), the material conventional PCR tubes are made of. In addition to a high surface/volume ratio (3.33 in our case) due to our chambers geometry, these characteristics result in an improvement of heat transfer, an essential factor in thermocycling^[53].

Before each assay, the inlets and outlets are sealed with a plastic foil to prevent evaporation, step (iv). The device and the plastic foil contain a cavity in its center to measure the coverslip's temperature with the IR sensor found in the center of the HyBOT lid.

During PCR, the critical stage for the formation of bubbles is the initial denaturation step^[54]. This step is carried out at 90-95°C for up to 10 min^[38]—depending on the type of DNA polymerase used^[54]—which can lead to sample evaporation and air bubble formation. Thus, we methodically studied how to prevent this effect by applying a degassing step for several time intervals (45 s, 3, 6, and 9 min) and absolute pressure conditions on the vacuum channel (250, 350, 450, 650 and 950 mbar). For this test, we acquired photographs at the beginning of the experiment and the end

of the initial denaturation step (**Figure S1**). We observed three different behaviors in the PCR chambers at the denaturation step: filled with liquid, with bubbles present, or emptied, **Figure 2d,e**. These behaviors depend on the capacity of the chip to absorb air through the PDMS. For example, for 950 mbar, at least one chamber had all the solution expelled to the inlets/outlets because of the expansion of some bubbles. The same effect was observed when the degassing step was applied for 45 s at 450 and 650 mbar. Air bubbles developed in at least one chamber when the pressure was set to 650 mbar and 450 mbar for at least 3 min, and when they were degassed for 45 s at 350 mbar. However, all the chambers remained bubble-free at 250 mbar and 350 mbar when degassing for at least 3 min. To explain these results, it is possible to calculate the volume of air absorbed in the PDMS over time. The difference in pressure between the chambers and the vacuum channel creates a volumetric trans-membrane flux, N , through the PDMS wall defined by the following relation^[55]:

$$N = \frac{p \Delta p}{b} \quad (1)$$

where b is the thickness of the PDMS wall, Δp the pressure difference between the channel and the outside, and p is the permeability of the material. For example, for O_2 in PDMS $p = 800$ barrer, in contrast for a thermoplastic such as PMMA, $p = 0.155$ barrer, more than 3 orders of magnitude larger and explaining the suitability of PDMS to degas the contents of the PCR chamber.

The time that it takes to absorb a certain volume of gas in the PDMS, V_{STP} (assuming standard conditions), can be defined by the following relation

$$t = \frac{V_{STP}}{N \cdot A} \quad (2)$$

where A is the area that of the vacuum channel that faces the PCR chamber.

By considering the distance b between the PCR chamber and the vacuum channel is 1 mm, and the area A is 15 mm², we can calculate the total volume of gas absorbed for all the conditions shown in **Figure 2d** using Eq. 1 and 2. Based on our observations and these calculations (**Figure S9**) we can conclude that conditions that absorb less 2.7 μL at absolute pressures higher than 450 mbar lead to the formation of bubble because of insufficient gas absorption in the PDMS walls. In general, bubble-free PCR chambers can be achieved under conditions that absorb more than 1 μL of air at absolute pressures less or equal than 350 mbar. Interestingly, in our calculations some gas absorption conditions overlapped, suggesting that lower absolute pressures, rather

than the degassing time, are more efficient in removing air bubbles. In our HybOT, we employ a miniature vacuum pump that generates 350 mbar to degas the PCR chamber for at least 5 min ensuring that no bubbles appeared during the PCR assay. In combination with the microfluidic device, this simple setup, allowed us to carry out experiments without bubbles that could interfere with the optical sensor measurement.

Optothermal performance. We studied the thermal characteristics of our instrument by measuring the temperature of the heating plate and the microfluidic chambers, **Figure 3a**. Using an infrared camera, we found the temperature of the heating plate to be uniform (standard deviation of $\pm 0.68^\circ\text{C}$), **Figure 3b**. Next, we compared this temperature to that inside the microfluidic chambers using a thermocouple. As shown in **Figure 3c**, at steady state, the temperature difference between the plate and the PCR chambers is of -0.48°C and 1.29°C for the 95°C and 65°C temperature setpoints, respectively. The difference in temperature between all the chambers was $\pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$. In summary, this characterization demonstrates a good temperature uniformity of the heating plate and in the microchambers.

We implemented and tuned a Proportional Integrative Derivative (PID) controller to precisely regulate the temperature in each step of the reaction. To achieve faster down ramps, we kept the TEC at 60°C using an on-off controller and a heat sink. On the surface plate, our PID controller achieved a heating rate and a cooling rate of 4.1°C/s and 2.8°C/s , respectively, **Figure 3c**. Whereas the temperature readings of the samples within the reaction microchambers showed similar heating and cooling rates of 4.06°C/s and 2.8°C/s , respectively. Although the chip is almost made entirely from PDMS (thermal conductivity: $0.15\text{--}0.22\text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), heat is conducted by the coverslip (glass' thermal conductivity of $1.4\text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) which is in direct contact with the PCR solution, **Figure 3c**. Commercially available thermal cyclers report rates for the heating block from 3.8 to 6.4°C/s and 3.9 to 5.9°C/s for the up and down ramps^[56], respectively. However, the sample temperature rates are typically lower, ranging from 3.4 to 4.6°C/s for the up ramp and from 2.8 to 4.3°C/s for the down ramp^[56], similar to those achieved by our HybOT Cycler.

The temperature profiles do not present a noticeably overshooting —reaching a maximum temperature deviation of 0.48°C at the 95°C setpoint— with no undershooting observed. These results suggest we achieved a critically damped PID controller, exhibiting an optimal compromise between response time and temperature accuracy. However, an overdamped response when reaching 60°C effectively reduced the step length and could lead to poor performance due to

Figure 3. Optothermal characteristics of the HybOT cycler. (a) Top-view photograph of the heating plate without (left) and with the device (right). The bottom schematic shows the location of temperature sensors. (b) Average temperature of the heating plate from 30 to 95°C. Inset shows a thermal picture of the heating plate with the dotted area highlighting the area analyzed. (c) The temperature profile of a single cycle was measured on the plate (IR) and in the microfluidic chambers (TC). The programmed temperature (PT) is shown in gray color. (d) Temperature profile of the heating plate under different external temperatures. (e) Correlation of fluorescence signals between the HybOT cycler and an inverted fluorescence microscope (Zeiss). (f) Fluorescence readings of the light sensors for three concentrations of fluorescein during 40 thermal cycles (red curve).

incomplete elongation, **Figure 3c**. To compensate for this reduction, we increased the step length by 5 s to guarantee that the reaction chambers stayed at 60°C for a sufficient time. Additionally, under different external temperatures: 5, 15, 27, and 40°C, our HybOT Cycler reached the same temperature profiles, **Figure 3d**. In summary, our thermal control system provides a similar performance to its benchtop counterparts.

Next, to characterize the fluorescence detection system, we compared the fluorescence signals from solutions of fluorescein (0 to 1 μM) measured with our instrument and a high-end inverted fluorescence microscope. As shown in **Figure 3e**, there is a strong correlation between both systems ($R=0.98$) demonstrating that our instrument performs similarly to a fluorescence microscope despite not having any optical components other than the light detector. We realized that overheating the light sensors led to inaccurate readouts (**Figure S10**) but adding a heatsink and a fan above them solved this issue. To verify their proper performance, we simulated a complete PCR assay (40 cycles) for three different concentrations of fluorescein (0, 0.3, and 0.6 μM). As shown in **Figure 3f**, the fluorescence signals remain practically unchanged during the assay, probably for the reduced excitation intervals since each PCR cycle reads fluorescence for only 200 ms. These results indicate that changes in sensor readout will be due to PCR amplification and not because of temperature-induced noise.

The optical filters we employed are made of UV grade fused silica with a softening point of 1585 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Corning 7980 substrate) which clearly surpasses the temperatures reached by our device. The filter hard coatings meet the US military standards and specifications MIL-C-48497A and MIL-STD-810F for environmental durability, with a maximum tested operation temperature of 85 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (67-031 and 67-028, Edmund optics), which is slightly below the PCR operation temperatures. However, we performed at least 100 PCR experiments using the same filter and did not notice a degradation in filter performance. In addition, the high-power LEDs in our instrument have an operating and storage temperature of -40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 135 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (LXML-PB02, Phillips Lumileds) and are therefore suitable for PCR.

PCR assays. We characterized the gene amplification efficiency and limits of detection of the HybOT system and compared its performance against a commercial benchtop thermocycler (StepOne™ Real-Time PCR System, Thermo Fischer). We obtained amplification curves for different RNA concentrations of the N1 gene of SARS-CoV-2 that ranged from 10^7 to 10^2 copies/ μL and a no template control (NTC), using both the StepOne (**Figure 4a**) and the HybOT, **Figure 4b**, **S11**. Next, to demonstrate the reproducibility of the assays carried out in the microfluidic chambers of the HybOT system, we obtained the cycle threshold (C_T) values of each dilution and calculated the coefficient of variation (CV) for intra-assays, **Table S2**. The CV in C_T values ranged between 1.4 and 5.4 % with an overall CV of 2.9 ± 1.4 %. Typically, for medical instruments a CV of <5% is defined as good, while a CV of 5-10% is regarded as acceptable^[57]. Furthermore, we assessed the inter-assays performance of the HybOT by running five

independent experiments in different days employing a concentration of 10^7 copies/ μL , **Figure S12**. As evidenced in **Figure 4c**, we found that the C_T values obtained from the inter-assays were not significantly different among them and had a mean of 22 ± 1.1 and a CV of 4.8 %. Overall, our intra- and inter-assay analysis demonstrate the reliability and consistency of our approach to detect nucleic acids, particularly the N1 gene of the SARS-CoV-2.

To demonstrate how qPCR efficiency (defined as the fraction of target DNA replicated in a PCR cycle) can help in setting a proper fluorescence detection threshold value, we generated standard curves while the threshold was varied between 0.1 and 0.5 of normalized fluorescence intensities in both systems. Fluorescence intensities were normalized between 0 and 1 (baseline and the maximum fluorescence intensity provided by the amplification curve of the highest concentration, respectively), for both systems. The efficiencies for each threshold were then plotted against the

Figure 4. Detection of SARS-CoV-2 N1 gene. RT-qPCR amplification curves showing mean and standard deviation for different dilutions of RNA of the N1 gene obtained with (a) a benchtop thermocycler (StepOne) and (b) the HybOT Cyclor. (c) RT-PCR inter-assay performance. (d) Analysis of PCR efficiency of both thermocyclers at various normalized thresholds to aid in defining proper thresholding. (e) Standard curves for threshold cycle values (C_T) as a function of RNA concentration. Error bars show the standard deviation (n=4).

normalized fluorescence intensity threshold, **Figure 4d**. PCR efficiencies of the benchtop system remains high through all threshold variations at ~100 % efficiency. In contrast, the HyBOT system exhibits an efficiency of ~90 % in the 0.1-0.3 interval and decreases to ~80% as the threshold level increase ≥ 0.4 . This is because at low thresholds the amplifications curves cross the threshold during the exponential phase, whereas at high threshold levels, the amplification curves cross the threshold during the linear phase, leading to a reduction in the PCR efficiency.

Higher efficiencies, and therefore better quantitative data, is achieved in the exponential phase because primers and substrates have not become depleted. Thus, thresholds should be adjusted within a window when amplifications curves cross the threshold during the exponential phase^[58]. The maximum efficiency achieved by the HyBOT system was 92.7% at a 0.2 normalized threshold whereas for the benchtop system the maximum efficiency was 100% at a 0.5 normalized threshold. To further compare the HyBOT performance against the benchtop system, we also obtained a RNA SARS-CoV-2 N1 gene calibration curve of the StepOne instrument, in this case employing the 0.5 normalized thresholds. As shown in **Figure 4e**, the optimized calibration curve from the HyBOT system shows an increase of ~3 cycles in the C_T for all RNA concentrations with respect to the benchtop system. Overall, we demonstrated that, together with the microfluidic device, the HyBOT Cycler could amplify samples with RNA copies as few as $10^2/\mu\text{L}$.

Finally, we evaluated the utility of our HyBOT Cycler in detecting the SARS-CoV-2 virus and benchmarked its performance against the StepOne, **Figure 5a**. We analyzed samples from 20 patients previously diagnosed with the virus and ten negative controls. We observed high variations in the viral load values for the positive samples detected with the HyBOT than with the Step One (**Figure 5b**), probably because of the slightly lower efficiency observed in transcribed RNA assays (**Figure 4e**) and because the microfluidic device can affect the reverse transcriptase enzyme by unspecific absorption to the PDMS surface. Nevertheless, using the HyBOT Cycler we were able to detect 19 of 20 samples positive for the virus, while all the negative controls were identified correctly; this translates into a sensitivity and a specificity of 95% and 100%, respectively, as shown by the ROC curves, **Figure 5c**. Overall, this experiment demonstrates the ability of the HyBOT cycler to detect the presence of viral RNA from human samples.

Figure 5. Detection of SARS-CoV-2 from clinical samples. (a) Workflow for detecting SARS-CoV-2 in 20 positive samples (+) and 10 negative controls (-). Samples are collected from a nasopharyngeal swab, prepared for RT-qPCR, then divided and assessed in both thermocyclers. (b) Violin plots show the viral load for 20 COVID-19 positive samples (P) and ten negative controls (N) obtained with both thermocyclers. (c) Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for HybOT (blue) and StepOne (red). AUCs: areas under the curve.

Conclusions

COVID-19 has emphasized the worldwide scarcity of tests and instruments to detect the virus SARS-CoV-2, in part because of an unexpected high demand and because some of them are manufactured in countries where governments banned companies from exporting to other nations until satisfying their internal demand. Under these circumstances, it is clear that we need to develop alternatives that can be (i) manufactured locally (ii) without much training, (iii) ideally from off-the-shelf parts, and (iv) using digital fabrication tools (that are now available worldwide). Our contribution in this direction was to develop a simple yet reliable instrument to perform RT-qPCR—the gold standard to detect SARS-COV-2. As we laid out in this paper, our HybOT Cycler consists of a hybrid module that works simultaneously as a heating element and as an illumination

source. This simple configuration also enables detecting fluorescence signals by regular light sensors, with no additional optics. We also developed a microfluidic device to carry out 4 PCR assays in parallel. The device is connected to a portable vacuum pump to eliminate any bubbles during PCR. Notably, the mold of this microfluidic device can be manufactured with a milling machine and does not require access to a clean room facility. Finally, and more importantly, we correctly identified 19 out of 20 patients infected with the virus, while no false positives were identified.

Our thermocycler can be repurposed for other similar assays, such as isothermal amplification methods. The HybOT Cycler's low weight (~1 Kg) and portability open the door to myriad applications, from its use in remote locations, homes, and clinics, to field applications such as monitoring water pathogens. Its wireless operation, together with GPS localization, means that real-time reports can be communicated to a centralized site (e.g., government facility, data center). The information can be employed to enact measures or to build epidemiological models^[32]. Furthermore, remote monitoring and control could enable field deployment while minimizing the risk of exposure and play an important role in halting the spread of COVID-19.

The HybOT Cycler, however, has some limitations. The concentration of some reagents in the master mix (BSA, enzymes, nucleotides) could be optimized to obtain more reliable amplification curves. The dimensions of the chambers and their volume could be re-engineered to reduce the unspecific absorption of reagents. A shortcoming of our device could be the few assays that can run in parallel, but we are working on a future version to increase the number of chambers to 16. Nevertheless, the cost of the HybOT components (~US\$700), a fraction of a commercial thermocycler (>US\$10,000), and the facility to build it outweigh these current limitations.

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Supporting Information

The following files are available free of charge. **Video S1:** Video shows loading the microfluidic device with PCR solutions, sealing it with optical adhesive film, and placing it on the HyBOT Cyclers. Additional Figures S1-S12 and Tables S1 & S2 are included in the Supplementary file.

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